

A Review On Communication Theories And Practices In Health Perspective

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Introduction

An understanding of communication theory and practice requires reflection on the literal meaning of the word communication. health communication as similar with the form of communication which should be based on exchanging information between health care providers and patients. Scholars from the healthcare often attributed malfunctioning within medical systems to the miscommunications that occur between health care professionals and between health care teams and their respective patients (Institute of Medicine, 2000). Generally, in the health care perspective, communication accessible and create understanding and sympathy among health care professionals and patients. Literature pointed theory in healthcare communication research is used to understand, explain and predict health beliefs, attitudes, intentions, and behaviors of individuals, dyads, groups, and mass audiences (Cameron, 2009). Theories presented herein were selected following careful deliberation among the authors as well as experts in the field of healthcare communication. Not all theories presented here were developed by interpersonal communication scholars; however, each chosen theory has had recent and robust work in communication. Health communication is influenced by different disciplines and theoretical approaches. Some of the most important theories can be divided into behavioral and social science theories, mass communications theories, marketing and social marketing, and other theoretical influences, including medical models, sociology, and anthropology. The review focuses on selected theories as well as its potential impact on health communication practice.

It is significant to develop good communication in health care setting specifically between health care professionals and the patients (Gambrill, 2012). Scholars pointed it is dynamic for health care professionals develop good communication skills with patients in the treatment needs and process (Hepworth, 2010). In addition, literature also pointed health care professional would practice communication techniques to create a better health care environment (Counoyer, 2013). Communication vary, including, for instance, verbal and non-verbal forms. There are also many approaches through which good communication relationships can be fostered (or hampered) and it is imperative, therefore, that care staff learn from best practice so as to ensure that they maximise the potential for the development of a meaningful relationship (Reeves et al., 2011). Good communication and interpersonal skills are, quite simply, essential to the practice of effective health and social care (Greenhalgh, 2008).

Communication in healthcare Perspective

As Street (2003) points out, medical consultations, like other types of social interactions, are dynamic, creative, and generally socially constructed events. First and foremost, communication is perceived as a "conversation" because different partners exchange information, make decisions, and build or maintain relationships. The nature and quality of the interaction depends on how participants select, adjust, and adjust their responses to

achieve their goals. Edelmann (2000) suggested that most clinical encounters can be thought of as an interaction between two different "cultures" (medical culture and patient culture). The two groups often have different ideas about health and illness, with different perceptions, attitudes, knowledge and goals. While patient agendas reflect their own illness experiences and their thoughts and expectations for counselling and treatment, healthcare provider agendas reflect their medical or other health-related education and personality. Reflects various background factors.

According to the literature, most healthcare encounters have two basic goals, including instrumental tasks such as providing information and questions, and social emotional tasks such as building partnerships (Roter & Hall, 1989). The two task types have different results because adherence and memory tend to be indicators or results of task-related characteristics of the device, and patient satisfaction is more related to the social and emotional aspects of the interaction. Suggested that it is related. Different participants in healthcare encounters will have different communicative styles. Research has shown that individual healthcare providers vary in terms of how often they provide information, use partnership building and display reassurance. Key factors that influence this include the provider's age, sex, level of education, personality and values. Thus, for example, women doctors have been found to spend longer with patients, and to spend more time addressing their social and emotional needs (Roter & Hall, 2004).

Despite these general differences, it has also been noted that healthcare providers tend to adapt their style of interaction in inconsistent ways according to the nature of the patient. Thus, for example, healthcare providers often use a more serious manner, focus more on physical and technical aspects, and assume more control with patients who are more seriously ill. Individual patients will also differ in their style of interaction depending on such things as their age, sex, ethnic background, level of education, and personality. Not surprisingly, these differences affect the nature and quality of interactions. Several studies have reported, for example, that patients who frequently ask questions and offer opinions generally receive more information and elicit more support and reassurance from healthcare providers than those who participate less.

Northouse and Northouse (1998) found that, in addition to specific personal and professional traits, healthcare provider-patient relationships can serve as potential barriers to effective communication and relationship building. I have discovered that it is affected by two factors. The factors are as follows: 1) Uncertainty about the particular "role" expected of the patient. 2) Uncertainty about who is responsible for dealing with certain aspects of the disease and caring for the patient. 3) Asymmetric "force" relationships (medical professionals have more power than usual). 4) The fact that healthcare providers tend to use medical terms that patients are unfamiliar with. In addition, Davis and Fallowfield (1994) point out that most of the communication problems encountered in healthcare interactions are caused by healthcare professionals making some very fundamental mistakes. This includes not introducing yourself, not asking the patient for explanation, not allowing or encouraging the patient to ask questions, not asking about the patient's feelings, and not providing information in a way that the patient can understand.

Like other professions, medicine has its own terminology, and healthcare professionals and patients can express themselves differently. Health providers may be able to switch from medical terms to everyday languages, but they tend to be overly dependent on medical terms and are often difficult for patients to understand. Hadlow and Pitts (1991) found that patients only understood the common language used by medical professionals, and the use of technical language was particularly problematic. On the other hand, some medical professionals, especially the elderly, adolescents, and some ethnic groups, rely mostly on the "baby language" of patronage when dealing with patients. Talking to patients can lead to frustration, lack of satisfaction, and poor health, as well as excessive reliance on medical and technical terms.

Doctor-patient communication

According to On et al. (1995) The doctor-patient relationship is one of the most complex interpersonal relationships. It involves interactions between unequal people, is often involuntary, affects critical issues, is emotionally appealed, and requires close cooperation. When assessing patterns of control and communication in a doctor-patient relationship. Scholars explain four basic forms of a) standard, b) paternity, c) consumerism, and d) commensalism (Roter & Hall, 1992). Failure relationships are categorized by lack of control on either side and are clearly far from ideal. Paternalism is described by dominant physicians and passive patients, while consumerism focuses on patient rights and medical obligations and is associated with the opposite. After all, reciprocity is defined by mutual decision-making and is often advocated as the best type of relationship. However, it is not suitable for all types of patients and is often difficult to achieve in practice.

Fallowfield et al. (2002) emphasizes that effective communication between physicians and patients can have many positive effects. Therefore, it is an important factor in the accuracy and completeness of data collection regarding symptoms and side effects, identifying problems that occur, influencing adherence to recommended treatments, and influencing mental and physical well-being. Contributes to patient and clinician satisfaction. Many patients experience some concern and fear when they see a doctor, and their levels also affect their interactions. Hospitalization can be a particularly daunting experience. In such cases, patients are often in an

unfamiliar environment away from family and friends, losing personal space, privacy, and independence, and often feeling anxious about health problems and their treatment. These factors often make them feel very vulnerable and can affect the way they interact with medical professionals.

Interestingly, doctors and patients have very different views on what they consider to be the most important factors in doctor-patient communication. Paling (2004) described a simple research project that asks doctors and patients what they think will be good doctors. Doctors said that "diagnostic ability" was the most important quality of a good doctor, and patients said that "listening" was the most important aspect. A study showed that doctors actually reflect the tendency to spend more time on medical technology questions (Cork, 2005). They conducted an observational study of doctor-patient interviews based on standardized clinical scenarios involving fictitious patients with high-risk surgery and severe comorbidity. The findings show that the medical situation is well explained by almost all physicians, but the patient's functional status, values, and fears have been poorly or minimally discussed. This difference emphasizes the fact that majority of physicians are trained in a highly medical or disease-focused counselling direction and this approach tends to be maintained throughout the medical career. It is clear that doctors need to communicate with patients to achieve many different goals.

A. Communication Accommodation Theory

In communication science, CAT is known as the theory of communication adaptation and was developed by social psychologist Giles, who sought to explain dialect variations and word choices that depended on communication partners (Giles & Powderland, 1975). CAT focuses on how individuals change their communication behavior as a result of communicating with each other. CAT is applied in medical communication to predict and explain changes in non-verbal and linguistic behaviors that providers and patients make to generate human behaviors and maintain or shorten the social distance of interactions. CAT examines interpersonal relationships from an intergroup perspective and describes attitudes, motivations, intentions, and identities that interact with social and contextual factors that influence communication decisions and outcomes (A. D'Agostino & Bylund, 2014).

CAT used in healthcare to predict and explain changes in linguistic and non-verbal behavior that healthcare providers and patients add to their behavior, often creating, maintaining, or reducing social distance in interactions. You can. CAT describes how behavioral strategies such as speech speed, eye contact, and gestures are used to adapt verbal and nonverbal behavior (Miller, 2002; Giles, 2008). Street (1991) was the first company to apply CAT to medical interactions. Since then, many studies have used CAT to investigate communication behavior in medicine (Watson and Gallois, 1998, 2002; A. D'Agostino & Bylund, 2011). However, because the donor-patient relationship is unique, not all aspects of the interaction are expected to be indicated. Therefore, some behaviors need to be complementary as they work to maintain communication differences between healthcare providers and patients in their respective roles.

B. Social Cognitive Theory

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) (Bandura, 1977, 1986, 1997) describes behavior as a result of three interactors such as a) behavior, b) personal factors, and c) external events. SCT is a behavior-oriented approach to understanding the effects of individual cognition, environment, and behavior on behavior and developing theoretical interventions to improve social health and inequality. Behavior is considered to be influenced by a combination of personal and external factors and events. One of the most important assumptions of SCT is to focus on the external environment, which is the source of observational learning. Another study showed that SCT refers to philosophies where individual understandings or thoughts are experimental as processes concerning visible stimuli and reactions in real life experience. Scholar also related to the situation where patient has to understand the doctors who are in the common environment with given behaviour for example, doctors behaviours associated with the communication with their patients (Vimala, 2016).

Action and decision of a doctor plays a very important role while communicating with patients. Behaviour of doctors with full morale value like being humble, caring, and supportive, will create a sense of belief in patients that their health related problems can be overcome. Positive and immediate action of a doctor towards the patient's health related issues may help patients get solutions for their health issue through proper medical advice. Decision of the doctors must be according to the patient's condition. In this case both doctor and patient must cooperate in deciding the appropriate solution for the health issues faced by the patient. According to the SCT, the environment is a place where individuals are motivated by personal and interpersonal influences to observe their behavior, understand its consequences, and adopt it repeatedly. SCTs are widely used for a variety of beneficial and detrimental behaviors and are successfully used in different interventions in different cultures. SCT can provide a framework for addressing several different issues in program research and planning, but its major contribution to health communication influences retention, reproduction, and motivation in specific behaviors.

C. *Interpersonal Communication Theory*

In the field of health, the means of communication mix is based on interpersonal communication. Interpersonal communication is the first human spiritual tool in the socialization process, takes place between two people in the context of their relationship, and helps negotiate and define the relationship in the course of their development. Defined as communication. His work "Psychology of Communication. Jean Claude Abric (2002) defines communication as" a set of processes that carry out the exchange of information and meaning between people in a particular social situation. " According to the author, "communication cannot always be understood as a simple interaction-based transmission process that is a transition between speakers. Output and reception are simultaneous, and the sender is the sender and the receiver, mainly the sender. Is a person "and the recipient (interrelationships also apply)". In his work "Language as a Means of Social Power", Blakar (1979) wrote that "the broadcaster provides all the information about his own person, his view of the object, through his message. Is a person. " Communication and social situations recognized, interpreted, and evaluated by the interlocutor, desired and recognized by him, provoke reactions, provoke connections, and block. Certo Samuel (2002) recommends that recipients be "always open when interacting with people with whom they are communicating and be careful not to convey negative attitudes through communication behavior" and message as recipients. Strive to consider the value of. They receive an attitude towards sources that should be taken into account without it. Otherwise, many valuable ideas will be lost if the message received is influenced by personal emotions.

D) *The Health Belief Model*

The health belief model was originally proposed by Rosenstock (1966) and developed by Becker and Rosenstock (1984) in the 1970s and 1980s. This model was the first analysis of health behavioral decisions, emphasizing that such decisions are a function of people's subjective perceptions of behaviors associated with potential health hazards. According to the model, perceived threats motivate people to take action, but beliefs about potential actions determine the specific plan of the attack. Threats can be manipulated in terms of both awareness of the severity of a particular health problem and awareness of a person's susceptibility to that health problem. This means that both factors must be emphasized in order for effective health communication to influence health beliefs. Relevant beliefs relate to the perceived benefits of appropriate behavior and the perceived obstacles to those behaviors.

Health belief models have been applied to a variety of health behaviors, including smoking, dieting, and exercising (Sheeran& Abraham, 1996). Several studies support this model. For example, studies show that healthy behaviors such as a healthy diet and regular exercise are serious health concerns, are susceptible to them, and all the benefits of adopting healthy behavior outweigh the costs. Has been shown to be related to the individual's belief (Harrison et al., 1992). However, other studies have reported contradictory results (Jenz&Becker, 1984). The primary criticism of the model is that the effects of the model's constructs, in terms of accurately predicting health behaviours, tend to be fairly small (Rutter and Quine, 2002), and that the model takes a rather static approach to health beliefs and does not sufficiently consider the temporal dynamic aspects (Schwarzer, 1992). Overall, the evidence suggests that although the beliefs specified by the model are prerequisites for preventative health behaviours, other cognitions are likely to be involved in prompting such behaviours.

E) *The Theory of Planned Behaviour*

While beliefs in health help people understand when they change their health behavior, it is also recognized that a complete model of health behavior requires more attention to behavioral intent and behavioral roles. The theory of planned behavior directly links beliefs in health to behavior (Ajzen, 1985, 1988). Scholar proposed to conceptualize intent as an action plan to pursue action goals. Intention arises from three factors or beliefs: attitudes towards behavior, subjective norms (including social norms and obsessions), and perceived behavioral control or self-efficacy. According to the model, these three factors predict behavioral intent, which is linked to behavior. Behavioral models based on Planned Behavior Theory (TPB) are designed separately for the communication behavior of social insurance physicians and beneficiaries, but are also combined during evaluation interviews. Other important concepts in the model are the assessment of communication behavior (satisfaction), intentions, attitudes, skills, and communication barriers. In general, empirical studies show that planned behavioral theories can predict a wide range of healthy behaviors, including exercise, vitamin intake, sunscreen, and contraception (Rutter and Quine, 2002).

Conclusion

This literature review has identified, to varying degrees, many theories classified as relational or structural that capture the complexity of health care practices and the nature of communication. These theories recognize the important role of relationships, mobilize knowledge, and incorporate interventions into everyday practice. From

this point of view, it can be a particularly useful implementation of medical theory. Although less noticeable in the literature, these theories are particularly applicable to health setting and service implementation. This study aims to enrich the existing knowledge and understanding of communication theory and practice in healthcare. The scope of research varies. It provides a general perspective on the theoretical and practical reasons that may represent the attitude of communication that may manifest in direct care provider interactions. Begin discussions among experts in this field about the potential, opportunities, and effectiveness of applications in theoretical and practical health systems that can guarantee higher quality medical services.

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